

Integration of plant structure information into process plant analysis and the student exchange with Helmut-Schmidt-University Hamburg

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Abstract: The systematic incorporation of information about a plant's structure can be helpful in the analysis of plant oscillations, fault propagation, alarm floods, etc.. With the rise of CAEX (= IEC 62424), plant structure information becomes available for automated, computer-based analysis. Nina Thornhill has explored these possibilities in cooperation with the author for more than a decade, and six exchange students from Hamburg had the honour to accomplish their Master thesis under the supervision of Nina Thornhill and have contributed to this endeavour. Further research works have been inspired.

Keywords: plant structure information, CAEX, IEC 62424, system modelling, automated HAZOP, Bond Graph models, alarm management

1. INTRODUCTION

The analysis of a multitude of process signals of a given process plant can reveal valuable insight. For example, the probable cause of a disturbance, e.g. valve stiction in a certain valve, which causes plant-wide oscillations, can be detected by comparison of the nonlinearity of the process signals. Nina Thornhill has provided important contributions to this field of research, e.g. in (Thornhill, Cox, Paulonis 2003). As described there, such algorithms usually yield a set of possible candidates for the cause, and a thorough process understanding is required to pinpoint the device, which causes the disturbance. In (Bauer, Cox, Caveness, Downs, Thornhill 2006), it has been shown that the direction of disturbance propagation in a plant can be detected based on transfer entropy, i.e. purely on the information contained in the data provided by process measurements.

However, Nina Thornhill was eager to systematically include information about the structure of the plant into the various analyses, as she wrote in (Thornhill and Horch, 2007): “*Detection of controller interactions and disturbances due to plant structure remain open issues, however, and will need new approaches. For the future, the linkage of data-driven analysis with a qualitative model of the process is an exciting prospect.*”

2. THE VALUE OF STRUCTURAL INFORMATION

Very early, Nina Thornhill had become aware of CAEX (Computer-Aided Engineering Exchange). CAEX is a meta-model for the description of hierarchical structures. It had been elaborated by Rainer Drath, Ulrich Epple, Alexander Fay and Murat Fedai for data exchange between CAE Systems which have different internal information models (Fedai, Drath, Epple and Fay 2003). This took place in a cooperation between ABB Corporate Research (Fay, Drath) and RWTH Aachen (Epple, Fedai). Originally, a CAEX model consists of a hierarchical model of all relevant objects (called

Internal Elements) in a plant (i.e. tanks, pumps, valves, sensors) and their links via pipes, which allow product flow between the objects. By references to *Role Classes* and *System Unit Classes*, it is possible to specify requirements and implementations of *Internal Elements*, respectively. While CAEX was originally mainly intended to ease the transfer of Pipe & Instrumentation Diagram (P&ID) content between CAE tools, CAEX was soon identified as a valuable information source for computer-based and, thus, automated analysis of plant structure information. Alexander Fay left ABB Corporate Research to become Professor for Automation Technology at Helmut-Schmidt-University Hamburg (henceforth: HSU) in 2004, and in the frame of a cooperation between ABB Corporate Research and HSU in the following years, methods were developed to automatically generate interlock control code for a continuous process plant (Drath, Fay, and Schmidberger 2006), based on a CAEX model of the plant. Similarly, it has been shown that asset monitors for plant objects such as boilers and heat exchangers can be created automatically (Schmidberger, Horch, Fay, Drath 2006).

Nina Thornhill was interested in investigating whether CAEX had the potential to provide the required information as stated at the end of Section 1. Therefore, she approached Alexander Fay in 2005, and they decided to let a student from HSU, with background in CAEX, explore the power of CAEX at the example of HAZOP analysis.

3. THOMAS HOLM (2005-2006): HAZOP

Thomas Holm (nee Scherf) spent the last two terms of his studies at UCL and accomplished his thesis under the supervision of Nina Thornhill and Lamia Banabbas. The idea was that Thomas Holm should develop an algorithm, which mimics a HAZOP analysis, based on a CAEX model of the plant under consideration. In a HAZOP study, all objects of a plant are investigated regarding the effects of deviations of pressure, flow, temperature etc. on this object (cause) and other

objects (consequences) which are linked to this object, primarily via pipes.

The approach that Thomas Holm pursued was

- to model typical potential deviations from normal operation and their related object types in a library, using a rule-based approach to describe possible consequences,
- to parse the CAEX representation of a plant, which was made available as an XML file, for Internal Elements which are instances of objects in the library,
- to explore the links of objects, as available in the CAEX file, to identify linked objects which would be affected by a deviation,
- to select from the library possible consequences.

The results were displayed as shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Results of an automated HAZOP analysis

The concept and implementation was evaluated by automatically carrying out parts of a HAZOP analysis for a North Sea gas rig. For this purpose, Thomas Holm added typical consequences of process deviations in gas rigs into the knowledge base. Fig. 2 displays results of the exemplary application.

Fig. 2. Results of an automated HAZOP analysis

The results were reasonable and could be confirmed by comparison with results of a manual HAZOP analysis of this plant, as reported in literature. The CAEX model proved to be a suitable source of information for a HAZOP study, although it contained only qualitative information about the objects and pipes, i.e. no lengths or diameters.

4. SEBASTIAN BEEZ (2007-2008): BOND GRAPH MODELS

Soon after Nina Thornhill had been appointed as ABB/RAEng Professor of Process Automation at Imperial College London (ICL) in April 2007, the student exchange scheme could be continued. Sebastian Beez spent the last two terms of his studies at ICL and accomplished his thesis under the supervision of Nina Thornhill and Jegatheeswaran Thambirajah in winter 2007/2008. Inspired by (Gawthrop and

Bevan 2007), Nina Thornhill and Alexander Fay encouraged Sebastian Beez to develop an algorithm to generate a Bond Graph model of a plant under continuous operation, on the basis of CAEX description of this plant's structure. Bond Graphs and CAEX have in common that they model a physical system as a set of lumped components, with defined connections. The types of connections, however, differ: whereas a CAEX model comprises of process flow connections, the connections in Bond Graphs are effort and flow, which yield power if combined. The main aim of Sebastian's work was to study to which degree these similarities can be used to automatically create Bond Graph models from CAEX models of process plants and a Bond Graph model library for typical plant components, provided by *Dymola*. Sebastian Beez managed to develop an algorithm that could fulfil these requirements for hydraulic processes. Fig. 3 displays the user interface for the application of the algorithm. In step 2, initial values for the state variables need to be set manually, all other steps can be carried out automatically.

Fig. 3. CAEX to Bond Graph transformation tool

Sebastian Beez successfully demonstrated an application of his algorithm by automatically creating a Bond Graph model of a pumped-storage hydro power station. The Bond Graph model could be simulated in *Dymola* and provided reasonable behavior in combination with a controller. Details of the algorithm and results of the application have been published in (Beez, Fay, Thornhill 2008).

5. MARCUS SCHLEBURG (2011): ALARM GROUPS

In 2011, Marcus Schleburg accomplished his Master thesis at ICL. Nina Thornhill and Alexander Fay had decided for a rather different topic this time: the handling of alarm floods.

During alarm floods, plant operators are overwhelmed by dozens or even hundreds of alarm messages in a time too short to react properly. Alarm floods have been reported as main causes of several plant hazards. Therefore, the management of alarm floods, i.e. the reduction of the numbers of alarms shown to the operator, is an important field of research. One approach to alarm flood reduction is, in case of unusual plant situations and a high number of alarm messages being created by the Process Control System, to suppress unnecessary alarm messages which do not provide additional information. Methods to figure out which alarm messages are unnecessary had been subject of international research for a while at that time, with moderate success. Suppressing alarms always implies the risk that an important alarm, which shows a new problem, independent of the previously identified problems, is wrongly classified and suppressed.

Plant disturbances cause process variables to deviate from their operation points, thus causing alarm messages. Such deviations of process variables propagate both upstream and downstream and cause other process variables to deviate, too, which results in further alarm messages. For example, low pressure in a pipe might result in low flow, and low flow might result in low level in the next downstream tank, and low level might result in high temperature if the tank is heated with constant energy input.

If one knows that two sensors in the plant are linked physically via the process flow, and both sensors raise alarms, it is very likely that these two alarms have a common cause. Such alarms should not be displayed independently to the operator, but grouped, to provide a better structure and overview and, thus, comprehension of the situation.

The idea which Marcus Schlegel elaborated on in his Master thesis was to automatically identify physical links between any two sensors in a plant, based on a CAEX model of the plant. Whenever two (or more) alarms occur within a predefined time window, his algorithm checks whether one of the alarms could have been caused by the same process variable deviation as the other one, due to a physical link between the two sensors. Furthermore, the qualitative means of propagation of process variable deviations have been collected by Marcus Schlegel and stored in a knowledge base. By application of this knowledge, every pair of alarms can be assessed regarding the possibility of a common cause. For example, two pressure alarms which pop up shortly one after the other and have a physical process link in between probably have a common cause. Some objects in the process link, however, reduce this probability, e.g. a pump, because pressure alarms on both sides of a pump could be independent from each other.

Marcus Schlegel managed to design and implement his algorithm and applied it successfully to historical alarm data. This data originated from two large process facilities in northern Germany. Figure 4 shows the result of an analysis of one of these alarm logs. The alarms which are not printed in bold in Fig. 4 have been grouped, because they have been identified as most probably having a common cause. This has afterwards been confirmed by the operators of this facility. The results of this Master thesis have been presented at the „Eu-

ropean Symposium on Computer Aided Process Engineering“ (ESCAPE) in London in Juni 2012.

Fig. 4. Grouped alarms

Later, results have been published in (Schlegel, Christiansen, Thornhill, Fay 2013), a journal paper which has been referenced, according to Google Scholar, more than 70 times.

6. SEBASTIAN SIEGERT (2012): STATUS INFORMATION FOR ALARM GROUPING

The work of Markus Schlegel had been a major breakthrough, but some ideas brought up in his thesis could not be dealt with by him due to limited time allowed for the thesis. One open issue was to be dealt with in the subsequent year by Sebastian Siegert. As noted in Section 5, objects in the process link between two alarm-raising sensors have an impact on the process flow between them and, thus, on the probability of these two alarms being dependent or independent. For some of these objects, the impact depends on their state. For example, a fully open valve has no impact on the propagation of flow or pressure or temperature deviations along the pipe. However, if the valve is fully closed, flow and pressure upstream and downstream are completely separated from each other, and no such deviation can be propagated along this pipe. To improve the reasoning whether two alarms can have a common cause, information about the state of the valve is necessary. The same holds for other actuators, such as pumps. The task of Sebastian Siegert was therefore to combine the alarm-grouping tool prototyped by Marcus Schlegel with a Process Control System. Thus, the alarm analysis could be carried out on-line, taking into account the current (and previous) states of the actuators. Fortunately, Nina Thornhill's lab was equipped with ABB 800xA PCS. Sebastian Siegert finally found a way to combine the ABB 800xA with the alarm-grouping tool, thus providing access to real-time state information. Special thanks to Martin Hollender at ABB who provided information about the alarm masking feature of ABB's alarm handling tool.

7. DENNIS SCHULZE (2013): PROCESS INFORMATION FOR REFINED DIAGNOSIS

In the previous works, the possibilities of using structural information, as it is usually displayed in a pipe and instrumentation diagram (P&ID) and made available in a CAEX file, had been investigated to automatically create simulation models, to carry out HAZOPs, or to detect possible causal relations between alarms. In the Master thesis of Dennis Schulze, the focus was on the diagnosis of plants, especially the root cause analysis, again by using a model of the plant's structure. For the root cause analysis of faults, the diagnosis expert needs structural as well as process knowledge to verify or falsify previously defined hypotheses. Especially in plants where batch processes are run, process-specific dependencies need to be taken into account, and a process model is required which describes the intended physical process. In the process model, the desired / minimal / maximal values of all process values should be defined and described. Dennis Schulze combined the structural model and the process model with knowledge about typical causal relations between symptoms and root causes. To support the diagnosis process, he derived a qualitative "diagnosis model" for the plant under consideration. In Figure 5, such a qualitative model is shown for a part of a plant.

Fig. 5. Qualitative diagnosis model

Based on the diagnosis model and in combination with the current process values, an automated diagnosis becomes possible, for a faster and more efficient detection of a root cause.

These works have been further extended by Esteban Arroyo and jointly published afterwards (Arroyo, Schulze, Christiansen, Fay, and Thornhill 2014). This paper presents a structured causal modeling approach to support the derivation of diagnostic models based on formalized process knowledge.

8. CAROLIN KIEFER (2014): PROCESS MINING, MULTI-AGENT SYSTEMS, PLANT ASSET MANAGEMENT

Carolin Kiefer carried out her Master project at ICL in summer 2014. In her work, she opened further directions for re-

search. One idea was to apply process mining techniques for the derivation of suitable causal models, allowing a better analysis of alarm sequences and alarming behaviour. Process mining has proven to be powerful on business processes, where all activities have an identifier, which allows to link them correctly to common causes. In signal traces gained from technical systems, only the time stamp and the sensor ID are available for each entry in the trace, which results in difficulties to group them properly. This has been dealt with at HSU for discrete manufacturing plants, see e.g. (Ladiges, Fülber, Haubeck, Arroyo, Fay, and Lamersdorf 2015).

Another idea which Carolin Kiefer investigated in her Master thesis was the use of Multi-Agent Systems to combine information from different sources, e.g. Alarm Management (AM) system and Plant Asset Management (PAM) system, to gain further insight into the alarm and event logs of a plant. In previous works, such as the one of Marcus Schlegel, it had become apparent in the evaluation of the examples that alarm sequences differ, depending on whether the plant (or plant section) was under maintenance. Taking into account when maintenance had been carried out (an information which is contained in the PAM) could help to better analyze alarm sequences.

9. CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

Over about a decade, six students from HSU had the opportunity to spend four to six months each under the supervision of Nina Thornhill. This has produced a variety of concepts and results, as sketched above. Some ideas had been developed to a level where results could be published on conferences or even in journals; other ideas have inspired further, subsequent work, some of them are sketched in the following.

Esteban Arroyo continued the combination of plant structure and process models for diagnosis purposes in a cooperation project with ABB Corporate Research (Arroyo, Chioua, Hornicke and Fay 2015) to support plant disturbance analysis by Dynamic Causal Digraphs and Propagation Look-Up Tables, and subsequently in his Ph.D. thesis (Arroyo 2017), this is described in more detail in another contribution to this book.

CAEX does not only allow to describe product flow but also energy flow and information flow, which can, in addition to product flow, be taken into account for the propagation of disturbances and, thus, for the assessment of alarms regarding the possibility of a common cause, see e.g. (Schlegel, Christiansen, Thornhill, Fay 2013) and (Arroyo, Chioua, Hornicke and Fay 2015). Nina Thornhill has also exploited this opportunity in (Romero, Graven, and Thornhill 2015) where they write: "While some of the relationships between elements are obvious from process descriptions, some others (recycle flows, utility systems, and electrical interactions) are not so easy to spot. The hypothesis is that information regarding these non-explicit connections is already available inside the diagrams and technical documentation of the process. This paper suggests a method for integrating electrical and logical connectivity with process connectivity extracted from "smart P&IDs"."

10. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

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Fig. 6. The author with Nina at lunch after the presentation by Sebastian Beez, 14.12.2007. Note the wine bottle and empty glasses.

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